

MODERN DESIGN PROPOSALS FOR EFFICIENT USE OF SPACE IN ONE-ROOM APARTMENTS IN HIGH-RISE AND MEDIUM-RISE BUILDINGS IN ARCHITECTURE.

Bekturdiyev Izzat Maqsudovich

Teacher. (UrSU)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7790544>

Annotation: This article presents modern design proposals on the effective use of one-room apartment space in high-rise buildings being built in developed countries around the world.

Keywords: one-room apartment, area, half-floor height, dimensions, projects, offers.

Today, in the developed countries of the world, the needs of the population for multi-storey residential buildings are increasing. In Uzbekistan, the construction of multi-storey residential buildings has developed greatly over the past 5 years, i.e. in 2018-2023. Multi-storey residential buildings are being built in all cities. As a result, there is a decrease in free land areas for construction of buildings in cities. Over time, the prices of residential buildings begin to rise. This has been proven in the experience of developed countries all over the world. The needs of the population for comfortable and small apartments are increasing. More residents with young families buy one-room apartments. Due to the fact that the area of one-room apartments is not very large, a number of inconveniences arise. It depends on the architects to find a solution. It is becoming an urgent issue for architects to design modern energy-efficient high-rise, multi-story and medium-rise residential buildings, and to place apartments in them very comfortably.

In this article, proposals are given to make the design of one-room apartments in multi- and medium-rise buildings more convenient and modern.

In this article, proposals are made to make the design of one-room apartments in multi- and medium-rise buildings more convenient and modern. The area of the common room is 16.5m², kitchen area is 13.2m², bathroom area is 3.4m². Figure 1

- Explication**
- 1. Corridor
 - 2. bathroom
 - 3. living room
 - 4. kitchen
 - 5. Balcony

Figure 1

This one bedroom apartment should have a height of 3.6m².

1-Offer to be given. the area of 7.5 m² of the common room is closed with a wooden or metal construction at a height of 1.8 m, and enough stairs are placed at this height.

Figure 2

2-Offer to be given. the 5.4m² area of the kitchen is closed with a wooden or metal construction at a height of 1.8m, and enough stairs are placed at this height. Figure 3

Figure 3

We can use the areas marked in red in Figure 3 as bedrooms. We can use the area above the common room as a bedroom for adults, and the area above the kitchen as a bedroom for young children.

In this one-room apartment, there are two bedrooms, an adult and a children's bedroom, a kitchen, a common room and other auxiliary rooms.

3-Offer to be given. comfortable furnishing of the apartment. It clearly shows the function of all the rooms. We can see this in Figure 4.

Figure 4

In the next picture, you can see the design of the apartment after it is equipped.

Figure 5

Conclusion: In the developed countries of the world, the construction of energy-saving and comfortable apartments, their equipment, efficient use of the space of one-room apartments is becoming an urgent issue. I think that if these proposals are used in the projects of one-room residential buildings, they can be another innovation in the field of architecture.

References:

1. Autodesk programs (AutoCAD, 3dmax)
2. Official mail of the Ministry of Construction.
3. Norms and rules of urban planning. SHNQ 2.08.01-2019

